

FINLAND

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE

FINNISH International Scientific Online
Conference:

«INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL
SCIENCE»

A collection of articles by Asian scholars

Issue 5, Part 1

Indexed databases:

aidlix.com

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference – Tampere, Finland «AID», 2025. Issue 5 Part 1.

Languages of publication: English, Russian, German, Italian, Spanish

The collection consists of scientific research of scientists, graduate students and students who took part in the International Scientific online conference «**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE**». Which took place in Tampere, 2025.

Conference proceedings are recommended for scientists and teachers in higher education establishments. They can be used in education, including the process of post - graduate teaching, preparation for obtain bachelors' and masters' degrees. The review of all articles was accomplished by experts, materials are according to authors copyright. The authors are responsible for content, researches results and errors.

© «AID», 2025

© Authors, 2025

SECTION 1. ARTICLES FROM ASIA

1.	MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS IN GOAL SETTING AND ACHIEVING THEM Urazbayeva Yulduz Abdullayevna	5
2.	The Role Of Extracurricular Activities In Educating A Socially Active Person Based On Moral Values Janny Cookel	9
3.	WPFDA STILLAR, TRIGGERLAR VA TEMALAR. Yusupov Mirsaid Abdulazizovich , Jurabayev Javohir	13
4.	LINQ SO'ROVLAR YARATISH Yusupov Mirsaid Abdulazizovich , Nurmatova Xushnozabonu To'ychiboy qizi	18
5.	WAYS TO ENSURE THE STABILITY OF NATIONAL PAYMENT SYSTEMS Hamroyeva Maftuna Axtamovna	25
6.	DIGITAL EVIDENCE IN CIVIL PROCEEDINGS Sanny Devy Loursen	31

**MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS IN GOAL SETTING AND ACHIEVING
THEM****Urazbayeva Yulduz Abdullayevna**

Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16732999>

Teacher of the Department of Psychology and Medicine, Mamun University

Abstract: This thesis analyzes the role of motivation in the process of setting and achieving goals in a person's life, its psychological and social aspects. The role of internal and external motives in goal-oriented activities, types of motivational factors and mechanisms of their formation are highlighted. Also, ways to increase motivation to achieve goals among students, students and young people are considered. The results of the study serve as an important theoretical and practical basis for developing motivational strategies and planning personal and professional development.

Keywords: motivation, internal motive, external motive, motivational factors, personal development, psychological motivation, motivational strategies.

Introduction.

The meaning of a person's life is often determined by the goals he sets and the actions he takes to achieve them. Each of us has some dream, aspiration or life point in our hearts - we move towards it, we act with it in mind. But the process of setting a goal and achieving it is not always simple and smooth. On this path, there is an important factor that pushes us forward, moves us, and gives us strength - this is motivation.

Motivation is a powerful engine of the inner world of a person, which plays an important role not only in personal life, but also in professional activities, education, sports and other areas. At the heart of any achievement lies deep motivation: someone wants to please their family, while another dreams of finding their place in society. It is this inner strength, faith in the goal that leads a person through difficulties and obstacles, teaches him perseverance and determination.

Modern psychology and pedagogy are paying more and more attention to the issue of motivation. Because in order for a person to achieve effective results in his life, he must have not only mental potential, but also a strong internal motive. Setting the right goals, building confidence in their implementation, and constantly encouraging them on this path have become an urgent issue, especially among the younger generation. The study analyzes the role of motivational factors in setting goals and achieving them, their types, formation, and practical significance. For a person walking towards a goal, motivation is a torch that illuminates the path. And when this torch does not go out, a person achieves his dream and finds blessings in his life.

Theoretical foundations.

The concepts of goals and motivation are one of the important objects of research in

psychology, pedagogy, and sociology. From a psychological point of view, a goal is a result that is consciously set by a person and must be achieved. Motivation is a set of internal or external factors that set in motion activities aimed at this goal. These concepts are inextricably linked and play a key role in determining the meaning of human life.

The theory of motivation has developed in psychology in several directions. For example, according to A. Maslow's theory of the hierarchy of needs, human actions and aspirations are based on certain needs. According to him, at the lowest level are physiological needs (food, sleep), followed by security, sociability, esteem, and finally, the need for self-actualization. A person strives for self-actualization, that is, to live a purposeful life, and this is the highest motivational level.

Also, in the theory of "Three basic motives" put forward by D. McClelland, human behavior is explained by three main forces - the need for achievement, the desire for power and the need for belonging. This model is especially used in the analysis of a person's activity in the social environment and professional motivation.

In pedagogical approaches, motivation is considered an integral part of educational activity. According to the theory of activity, formed on the basis of the scientific works of A. A. Leontyev, L. S. Vygotsky, S. L. Rubinstein, any educational or labor activity must have a motivational basis. This directs the person to the goal, gives meaning to the activity.

Modern psychologists divide motivation into two types: intrinsic motivation is the movement of a person based on his own interests, beliefs or values; extrinsic motivation is formed under the influence of reward, avoidance of punishment or external evaluators. Scientific research shows that intrinsic motivation is more important in achieving long-term and sustainable success. Self-motivation, setting realistic and clear goals, proper time management, and positive thinking are also considered to be one of the main components of motivation. These aspects increase the level of self-awareness of a person and form the ability to self-manage.

Analytical discussion:

The act of understanding a person's life, living it meaningfully and effectively largely depends on what goals a person sets for himself and on what motives he implements them. Each of us has different desires and intentions, but for these desires to become goals and come true, a strong internal drive is necessary - that is, motivation. The interesting thing is that some people achieve great heights in life despite having modest resources, while others, having all the opportunities, remain aimless. Why? The answer to this question is hidden in the analysis of motivational factors.

Motivation is the force that drives a person, which can manifest itself both consciously and unconsciously. A person with intrinsic motivation moves towards a goal based on his inner need, interest, and confidence. He perceives life's obstacles as opportunities, and considers problems as necessary tests for development. A person relying on extrinsic

motivation acts more under the influence of external evaluation, reward, position, or social pressure. Although both types of motivation are important in their own right, intrinsic motivation is the main factor for long-term success.

Proper management of motivational factors in the process of achieving goals requires self-awareness, discipline, proper time management, and a culture of positive thinking. The formation of these skills, especially among young people, is becoming an urgent task of the modern education system. Unfortunately, in some cases, negative situations such as lack of purpose, low self-esteem, lack of confidence, and dissatisfaction with external circumstances lead to motivational depression in students, which hinders the intellectual and social development of the individual.

Therefore, specific pedagogical and psychological approaches to the formation and support of motivation are necessary. When working with pupils and students, studying their interests, an individual approach, encouragement, setting goals step by step and planning them to an achievable level are important in strengthening the motivational system. In addition, it is possible to activate their internal motivation by building self-confidence in students and emphasizing positive results. Achieving a goal is not just a desire, but the result of a consistent plan, determination, willpower and constant motivational support. If a person has a goal, a path leading to it will certainly be found. But the clarity of this path, perseverance in overcoming it, depends on the correct formation and development of motivational factors.

Conclusion.

From the above analysis it follows that a person's finding his place in life, his aspirations and the results achieved are closely related, first of all, to the goal set and the motivational factors on the basis of which he acted. Clearly defining the goal, developing a strategy to achieve it, and motivating himself with internal or external motivations at each stage are the main pillars of the path to success. Motivation is the driving force of the human psyche. If it is formed, developed and directed correctly in a timely manner, the potential of the individual is fully manifested. Especially in the educational process, the formation of goal-oriented thinking in the younger generation, strengthening their internal motivation and strengthening self-confidence are urgent tasks of modern pedagogical activity. Therefore, in order to achieve high results in personal and professional life, it is necessary to set clear and meaningful goals, constantly self-assess and work in a motivational environment. After all, if the motivation is strong, a person is able to conquer any peak.

Reference list:

1. Leontev A.N. Deity. Soznanie. Lichnost. - M.: Politizdat, 1977. - 304 p.
2. Woodworth R.S. Psychology / Per. English - M.: Progress, 1990. - 458 p.

3. Vygotsky L.S. Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes. - Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1978. - 159 p.
4. McClelland D. Motivation is human. - SPb.: Peter, 2007. - 352 p.
5. Rubinstein S.L. Basic public psychology. - SPb.: Peter, 2000. - 720 p. Bodalev A.A. Lichnost i obshchenie. - M.: Prosveshchenie, 1981. - 254 p.
6. Jung K.G. Psychological types. - M.: Kanon+, 2019. - 624 p.
7. Ryan RM, Deci EL. Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being // American Psychologist. - 2000. - Vol. 55(1). - P. 68-78.
8. Inoyatova Sh. The importance of motivation in the modern education system // Journal of Pedagogical Sciences. – 2022. – No. 2. - B. 45-49.